

SZ-SB-III-03-01 Contacting teachers via BIRD (English)

Author	@Julia Lehmler ; @Ricarda Peil ; @Tara-Marie Endries ; @Alexande Schröter ; @Julia Victoria Dinier ; @Sönke Erdmann (original German version) @Jan Martin Kauter ; @Tara-Marie Endries ; @Emily Penk (English translation)
Doi	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14851258
ID	SZ-SB-III-03-01
Title	Contacting teachers via BIRD
Educational area	#school
Persona	P: Alvin - legal guardian https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10091406
Short description	Alvin Weierbach is moving from Brandenburg to Bavaria with his family. His daughters Lisa (16) and Lena (13) are changing schools in the middle of the school year, and he wants to make early contact with the new teachers.
Result	Alvin contacts the teachers.
Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Problem scenario• Activity scenario<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Process "First contact"
Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Alvin is registered at BIRD• Alvin is logged in to BIRD
Components	#buddyfinder #profile #chat #contacts
Services / tools	

Problem scenario

Introduction

Alvin Weierbach is moving from Brandenburg to Bavaria with his family. His daughters Lisa and Lena are changing schools in the middle of the school year, and he wants to establish early contact with the teachers.

Problem definition

Alvin wants to get all the information he needs before the move and is looking for an easy way to contact the schools and future teachers of his daughters.

Background and context

For Alvin, it's important to have everything in one place and not have to search for the individual information he needs. For him, this also includes communication with his daughters' new teachers, whom he would like to ask various questions. Alvin doesn't have the opportunity to speak to the teachers in person before the move; everything has to be done digitally. Lisa also finds this helpful because it allows her to ask questions to her future teachers and familiarize herself with the teaching materials to close any gaps.

Impact of the problem (on the Persona)

No contact with the teachers is not an option, especially in the middle of the school year. Alvin generally prefers personal conversation. He wants his daughters to have the best possible start at their new schools. This is important to Alvin because it makes the move less stressful. He won't have to deal with even more tasks at the beginning if he takes care of it now. In addition to the necessary information, it's also about getting an impression of the teachers and getting to know them in advance.

Pre BIRD attempts at a solution

Since the teachers in question are usually in class and therefore difficult to reach, he hasn't been able to reach them by phone yet. Email communication works well with the school administration but unfortunately not so well with the teachers.

Activity scenario

Process "First contact"

Step 1: Alvin navigates to the Learningpathfinder in BIRD and searches for contacts at his daughters' school. Some of these are anonymized, but Alvin can find the contacts of the new class teachers, whose names he received during registration.

Step 2: Alvin clicks on the profile of one of the teachers and sends her a contact request.

Step 3: Alvin receives a notification that his contact request has been accepted and he can now contact the teacher via chat.

Step 4: Once on the teacher's profile, Alvin can see the information provided by the teacher and that she is currently online.

Step 5: Now Alvin can start a chat with the teacher by clicking on the "Chat" button.